

Celtis africana

White stinkwood/Witstinkhout

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Importance:

The fruit and seeds of the white stinkwood (witstinkhout in Afrikaans) are consumed by various animals, including baboons, monkeys, doves, parrots, louries, thrushes, bulbuls, and weavers. The wood has traditionally been used as a timber to manufacture a variety of household articles.

Several related *Celtis* species have been introduced to South Africa and can be mistaken for the white stinkwood. These species are planted as shade trees in gardens and parks but also invade riverbanks and urban spaces. They can hybridize with the white stinkwood, highlighting the need for conservation.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 49.39 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 31.01 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.48 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.3% [Single: 99.1%, Duplicated: 0.2%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 45 733.9 kilobases

Contig number: 655

Sample Contributor contact details:

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Group: Eudicot

Size: Up to 25 meters tall

Distribution:

Celtis africana occurs in large parts of Sub-Saharan Africa .

It grows in a wide variety of habitats from forest and coastal bush to bushveld, mountain gorges and open country, typically savanna. Its range extends from the Western Cape, South Africa, eastwards and northwards around the southern African coastline, extending inland in the warmer, wetter regions, and further north into Ethiopia and the Arabian peninsula.